

A Proposed Model for Developing the Taxation System on Oil Companies in Iraq: A Strategic Framework for Budget Financing and Enhancing Economic Stability

Zaid Ali Ahmed ✉

College of Dentistry, Tikrit University, Tikrit, Iraq

Abstract

This study aims to implement the proposed recommendations to enhance the efficiency of the strategic management of the state's fiscal policy. This objective is pursued through the pivotal role played by strategic management within financial institutions, particularly in controlling and utilizing fiscal policy tools for the formulation, estimation, and execution of the state's general budget. The ultimate aim is to achieve the economic objectives set by the executive authority. However, these goals are often difficult to realize due to the state's heavy reliance on oil revenues and the pressing need to diversify income sources. To address this issue, a model has been proposed for imposing taxes on oil companies operating in Iraq, in light of the observed inefficiencies in the current tax system. Accordingly, the study recommends adopting clear strategic plans that contribute to achieving the goals of fiscal policy, enhancing social welfare, and improving the application of tax regulations.

Keywords: *Fiscal Policy, Strategic Management, Budget, Taxation, Oil and Gas.*

JEL Classification codes: *H25, G32.*

Suggested citation: Ahmed, Z.A. (2025). A Proposed Model for Developing the Taxation System on Oil Companies in Iraq: A Strategic Framework for Budget Financing and Enhancing Economic Stability. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(2), 182-197. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2025.2(2).17

Introduction

Fiscal policies represent one of the most significant challenges facing governments, as they embody the methods and structures utilized by the state or government in directing its economic programs, including revenues and expenditures, in accordance with the objectives defined by the prevailing political philosophy and governance system. As such, fiscal policy reflects the government's economic vision and provides a clear outlook on the strategic paths it intends to follow. States typically develop various plans to achieve the financial and economic strategies they outline, especially given the need to finance the budget through diverse sources. Consequently, it becomes imperative for governments to establish fiscal policies that ensure the mobilization of necessary funds from available resources to create a general state budget aimed at realizing the country's economic and social goals.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

The primary objective of fiscal policy is to achieve economic balance, that is, maintaining equilibrium between state revenues and expenditures to avoid financial deficits that may lead to a growing debt burden year after year. Simultaneously, fiscal policy seeks to promote social balance through the redistribution of income among different societal groups. Thus, the proper use of fiscal tools is essential for establishing a stable, balanced, and prosperous standard of living for all citizens. For this reason, the strategic management of fiscal policy is considered a fundamental pillar in keeping pace with contemporary developments and accompanying trends, particularly in terms of utilizing strategic tools and concepts that promote transformation and align with long-term financial visions to strengthen the state's fiscal policy.

Moreover, modern administrative trends have significantly contributed to the qualitative development of financial institutions by influencing and reshaping their operating environments. One of the most prominent of these trends is the optimal application of strategic management approaches in leading institutions to confront current challenges and enhance the state's administrative practices. Traditional mechanisms and methods previously relied upon are no longer sufficient for managing the future of state institutions, especially in the context of shifting global dynamics such as fluctuations in raw material and oil prices, upon which many economies heavily depend. This new reality necessitates the adoption of strategic management as the key determinant and driving force behind fiscal policy, serving as a regulator of government spending and taxation.

In this context, it is essential to consider several critical issues related to oil revenues and asset management and to propose a model for taxing exports of raw oil and gas materials.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in the critical role that strategic management can play within financial institutions by exercising control over the tools of fiscal policy to formulate the state's general budget. This includes the estimation and execution of the budget to achieve the economic and social objectives pursued by the executive authority.

Given the current economic and fiscal system in Iraq, the researchers propose a model for imposing taxes on the export of raw materials, oil, and gas. This approach aims to diversify the sources of budget financing amid fluctuations in global energy prices, especially considering the financial deficits that recent budgets have experienced. Such deficits have hindered the state's ability to fulfill its obligations and meet the goals of economic and social development.

Research Problem

The research problem centers on the weakness of Iraq's economic management, which heavily relies on the oil sector to address most economic challenges. Oil revenues account for approximately 95% of Iraq's total income. This overdependence underscores the urgent need to diversify revenue sources by exploring alternative options, including taxation.

Research Objective

The main objective of this study is to develop and support proposals aimed at reforming the tax system, taking into account the various factors that influence its development and effectiveness. These proposals are guided by the strategic goals of fiscal policy, which—like any economic policy—aims to ensure macroeconomic stability by counteracting the business cycle. Specifically, the study seeks to support fiscal strategies that contribute to:

1. Stable economic growth
2. Full employment of resources (primarily addressing cyclical unemployment)
3. Price stability (as a solution to inflation)

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation of the study is based on the findings of prior scientific research, including the work of both domestic and international economists in the fields of taxation and the design of tax models for oil and gas extraction. It also includes an exploration of methods to encourage and strengthen the tax system through incentives and policy reform.

Methodological Framework

The methodological foundation of the study relies on a wide range of legal and regulatory documents from the Republic of Iraq, in addition to scholarly literature addressing taxation-related issues. The study also draws on general scientific methods of knowledge acquisition, such as analytical (organizational, statistical, historical, schematic, and comparative) techniques. To ensure accurate synthesis and appropriate conclusions, the study employs integrated methodologies including induction, deduction, economic modeling, logical generalization, and measurement. These approaches form the empirical basis of the study, which incorporates legislative and regulatory procedures, statistical and analytical data from Iraq spanning the period 2000–2019, as well as scholarly publications from Iraqi and international journals relevant to the subject matter, in addition to the researchers' own calculations.

First: The Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of Strategic Management

Historically, the term "strategic management" was coined in the early 1960s and 1970s to distinguish between top-level executive management and operational-level management focused on production. In 1965, Igor Ansoff questioned earlier methods of long-term planning and proposed a model for strategic planning. Many prominent scholars contributed to the establishment of strategic management as a new system, including Alfred D. Chandler, Jr., Philip Selznick, Igor Ansoff, and Peter Drucker.

Strategic management refers to a sequence of actions undertaken by organizations to achieve long-term objectives that enable them to remain competitive and thrive in any environment. The more unstable the external environment becomes, the greater the organization's need for a clear and effective strategy (Aktionova, 2017).

Strategic management is one of the core functions of management, extending to the company's long-term goals and operations. The formulation of strategy (the course of action) and its associated tools represent the essence of management and a key indicator of sound corporate governance.

According to researchers, strategic management involves the development and implementation of actions that enable an organization to achieve superior long-term performance compared to its competitors. It is also closely tied to the full range of activities necessary for the effective operation of a business, including planning, environmental analysis, resource allocation, control, and organizational regulation.

1. The Importance of Strategic Management

The importance of strategic management lies in its ability to transform decision-makers into visionary leaders capable of formulating long-term goals and articulating far-reaching objectives. Within the work environment, strategic management holds a critical role as one of the most essential administrative processes, reflected in the following key points (Alive, 2017; Dahlia, Mustafa, & Yasir, 2023; Dahlia, Mustafa, & Yasir, 2023; Falko, & Somina, 2022; Guidolin, Hansen, & Pedio, 2019; Ibrahim, 2018; Karaev, et al., 2018):

- It provides an integrated system for monitoring and evaluation within a dynamic environment composed of interrelated functional subsystems. This includes analyzing these subsystems and the organizational climate, identifying strengths and weaknesses in these areas.
- Strategic management assists in redefining the organization's position, developing plans, and evaluating overall performance. It serves as a rational framework for selecting the most suitable strategic option among various alternatives.
- It can be employed as a proactive mechanism to anticipate and respond to crises and disasters.
- It aids in the allocation of scarce resources and ensures their efficient and effective utilization.
- Strategic management addresses both present and future concerns. It offers an inward-outward perspective and a forward-looking analysis of current conditions (Dahlia, Mustafa, & Yasir, 2023).

2. Content of Strategic Management

- Analysis of the internal and external environment
- Formulation of the organization's mission and objectives
- Selection and development of a corporate-level strategy and its analysis (e.g., SZH strategy)
- Design of the organizational structure
- Determination of the level of integration and control systems
- Definition of behavioral standards and corporate policy in specific areas of activity
- Evaluation of the company's performance and strategy, and the enhancement of organizational structure and management systems (Alive, 2017; Dahlia, Mustafa, & Yasir, 2023).

3. The Strategic Management Process

Figure 1. Illustrates the Strategic Management Process

Source: Prepared by the researchers.

Through Figure (1), it becomes clear that the strategic management process begins by identifying the work environment in which strategic management should operate and perform its functions in

a way that helps achieve the planned objectives. Following this, the optimal strategy is selected and evaluated for implementation to achieve the desired goals, and the strategic performance of the organization is assessed based on these objectives.

Second: Fiscal Policy and Its Tools

Fiscal policy involves the government's ability to collect taxes and allocate funds from the state's general budget in order to achieve the planned objectives. This policy, which governs public spending and taxation, is implemented by the executive authorities after being approved by the legislative authority, which controls the execution of tax operations through the enactment of the necessary laws.

Fiscal policy has the potential to influence government spending, thereby reducing the amount of money circulating in the economy, which could negatively impact fiscal policy in the future and lead to economic stagnation and high unemployment. However, if the government uses fiscal policy to adjust spending and tax rates in order to stabilize the economic cycle, the economy will not remain static forever (Moamin, et al., 2024).

Fiscal policy is primarily focused on regulating total supply and demand. In this context, the economy is managed by influencing the value of total expenditures. However, certain fiscal policy tools can be used to influence aggregate supply by affecting the level of economic activity. The government follows fiscal policy through which its financial tools aim to achieve national economic goals. The main objective of fiscal policy is the continuous growth of the national economy.

The key tools of fiscal policy include public budget expenditures and revenues, which are: 1) Expenditures. 2) Public Revenues.

Figure 2. Illustrates the Fiscal Policy Objectives of the Government

Source: Prepared by the researchers

Currently, the Iraqi economy is striving to improve and become better than in previous periods. Typically, fiscal policy involves organizing the state's budget and taxes to stimulate the economy. In this regard, it is essential to focus on two key fiscal policy tools: expenditures and taxes, which are closely interconnected (Muresianu, & Watson, 2021). The main directions of the budget are determined through the optimal use of the state's financial resources, as well as financing methods and the primary sources for replenishing the treasury's resources, with modern fiscal policy serving as a central component of financial charges. The main drawback of fiscal policy, according to a number of economists, arises from its goal of stimulating the economy by increasing government purchases of goods and services.

Third: The Budget and Its Financing Methods

1. The State Budget

The concept of the "budget" originally refers to a container and its contents—symbolically, it represents the financial purse under the stewardship of the Minister of Finance. From an economic standpoint, the state budget can be understood as the government's primary "money bag." One of its defining characteristics is its expanding influence on redistributing national income.

The state budget serves a dual purpose: it is both an economic concept and a financial blueprint. Economically, it embodies the financial interactions between the state, individuals, and legal entities regarding the allocation of national income and the establishment of a budgetary fund. As a financial document, it outlines government revenues and expenditures. In this role, the budget acts as a practical instrument for governance, illustrating the state's financial needs and guiding fiscal policies through targeted expenditure. In doing so, it shapes the national tax structure and facilitates the distribution of income and GDP, thus serving as a central tool for economic management (Guidolin, Hansen, & Pedio, 2019).

2. Principles for Structuring the State Budget

Five key principles underpin the preparation of the state budget:

1. Annuality
2. Unity
3. Balance
4. Comprehensiveness
5. Universality

The principle of comprehensiveness ensures that all government revenues and expenditures are accounted for. Budgets can be presented in gross or net terms: the gross budget includes all income and outgoings, including those linked to state-owned enterprises, while the net budget presents only the difference between revenue and spending (Dahlia, Mustafa, & Yasir, 2023).

Budget unity requires all financial activities of the state to be reflected in a single, consolidated document. This principle supports the coherent evaluation of fiscal performance and comparison across budget segments. To facilitate this, a standardised classification system is applied to budget items, grouping income and spending by shared features. The four main classifications include:

1. Administrative (based on ministries and agencies)
2. Functional or sectoral (e.g., health, defence, education)
3. Economic (e.g., capital expenditure, salaries, social transfers)
4. Combined or mixed classification, which uses a matrix-style format to cross-reference categories both vertically and horizontally.

Credibility, or budget realism, implies that revenue and expenditure figures must be substantiated and based on reliable projections.

Transparency is ensured through public presentation and legislative scrutiny of the budget during its approval process (Falko, & Somina, 2022).

3. Functions of the State Budget

The national budget serves several fundamental purposes (Shchegoleva, & Malsagov, 2019):

a) Redistributive Function

The redistributive role of the budget is evident in the accumulation and allocation of centralised funds across federal, regional, and local levels. In many industrialised nations, budgets manage the redistribution of up to 50% of GDP.

b) Stimulative Function

The budget acts as a tool for the state to influence economic dynamics. By directing fiscal resources to targeted sectors or regions, it can encourage or restrain production, influence the growth of private capital and savings, and modify the structure of both demand and consumption.

c) Social Function

Through social expenditures, the state allocates budgetary funds to finance essential public services such as health, education, and welfare, aiming to enhance overall societal well-being and support vulnerable populations.

d) Control Function

This function ensures accountability in the use of public funds. It provides a mechanism for the state to oversee both the collection and expenditure of financial resources, ensuring they are used in line with approved objectives.

The redistribution of a nation's gross domestic product (GDP) through its budget occurs via two interconnected and ongoing processes: the collection of revenues and the allocation of expenditures. These phases—revenue generation and the disbursement of budgetary resources—take place concurrently and are inherently linked.

Budget revenues refer to funds that are acquired by the state without compensation and are not subject to repayment. These revenues fall into two main categories: tax and non-tax sources. Tax revenues are derived from newly generated value and the primary distribution of income streams such as profits, wages, interest, rent, and savings. In most national central budgets, taxes comprise approximately 80% to 90% of total revenues.

Non-tax revenues, on the other hand, originate either from the government's own economic operations or through the redistribution of income already collected within different levels of the fiscal system. Examples of non-tax revenues include:

- Proceeds from the privatisation or lease of state and municipal assets
- Earnings from international trade and foreign economic engagements
- Revenue from the divestment of government-held shares (Pilipenko, 2012).

In contrast, budget expenditures represent the financial commitments made by the state and local authorities to fulfil their constitutional responsibilities and operational mandates. In market-based economies, budgetary outlays are typically structured around several core areas, such as:

- National security and defence
- Economic development and infrastructure
- Social services and cultural programmes
- Public administration
- Servicing of national debt obligations

Generally, these expenditures are non-recoverable, as they are intended to finance public goods and services rather than generate direct financial returns. However, in instances where the

government extends budgetary loans, such loans are expected to be repaid in accordance with defined terms. The composition of expenditures is revised annually within the fiscal planning process and is influenced by both macroeconomic conditions and evolving socio-political priorities.

4. Proposed Model for Taxing Raw Material and Oil Exports

1. Definition of Oil and its Economic Importance

Oil is a mixture of hydrocarbons, typically a dark-colored, oily, flammable liquid with a pungent odor and toxic properties. It is a mineral with a density similar to that of oily liquids, and when ignited, it releases a significant amount of heat. Oil is extracted from beneath the earth's surface at depths ranging from half a kilometer to six kilometers. Oil can also be defined as a complex hydrocarbon mixture, primarily composed of carbon (up to 87% of its total composition), with the remainder consisting of gases and non-hydrocarbon chemical components (hydrogen, nitrogen, sulfur, paraffins, oxygen, and organic chlorine compounds). Upon reaching the earth's surface, it transforms into substances like tar, natural bitumen, and asphalt, among others (Mustafa, Moamin, & Dahlia, 2022; Pilipenko, 2012; Romanov, & Kolchen, 2017).

The color range of oil varies from transparent yellow to pure black, with brown oil often exhibiting a dark green hue. Some oil fields produce emerald-colored oil, and the rare blue oil color can be seen in fields in Azerbaijan. The oil may have a light, somewhat pleasant odor, but it can also emit an unpleasant, repulsive smell that is intolerable to the human sense of smell. This characteristic is attributed to chemicals such as nitrogen, oxygen, and sulfur.

The chemical composition of oil consists of all the components of natural gas and natural fossil ozokerite, which are collectively referred to as fossil petroleum. In turn, petroleum belongs to the group of caustobioliths—flammable minerals of biological origin, which include various types of fossil fuels.

Despite the development of alternative energy sources, oil remains a crucial factor affecting the formation of local economies of countries, and thus, global economic development. On this basis, political relationships (treaties and agreements) between different countries and groups of countries are established. Their development strategies, among other things, are formulated with consideration of oil production and petroleum products (Mustafa, et al., 2019).

Global oil reserves are unevenly distributed and are not available to all countries. As a result, some economies are forced to include the costs of obtaining oil from other countries in their budgets, which in turn profit from it and spend the earnings on other purposes. This situation arises due to the need to use petroleum products in various industries.

The regulation of global oil prices is determined not only by the relationship between supply and demand but also by other factors such as volumes and production periods. To regulate the production and global price of resources, a special organization of oil-exporting countries OPEC was established (Wang, 2019).

Currently, "spheres of influence" and certain agreements have been formed, defining the scope of exports to various countries. For example, Western Europe buys oil from the Middle East, while the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States and Eastern Europe work with Russia. The Western Hemisphere is supplied with oil by South American countries, and the main energy resource suppliers in Asia are China, Australia, and Indonesia.

2. The Development of the Oil Industry and Its Impact on the Global Economy

The oil industry plays an extremely important role in the global economy. Oil is one of the most demanded resources and has played a key role in the development of modern society (Vallega, 2003). Its influence extends from energy production to the creation of a wide range of plastics and chemicals.

Firstly, the oil industry is a primary sector in both developed and developing countries (Tretyakova, Kuznetsova, & Polyakova, 2024). The industry contributes to the economy by creating jobs, generating government revenue, and fostering investment and economic growth. Many countries, such as Saudi Arabia, Russia, and the United States, rely on oil and gas revenues to support their national budgets and economic growth.

Additionally, the oil industry forms the foundation for energy production. Oil is the primary source of energy used in transportation, industry, agriculture, and households. It keeps the global economies running and ensures the transport of not only oil but also other goods across the world (Pilipenko, 2012).

The importance of the oil industry is also evident in the industries that are closely linked to it (Mustafa, Hammoodi, & Alsaady, 2024). Oil is used to produce a wide range of products such as polymers, plastics, fertilizers, pharmaceuticals, and more. These products are used in numerous industries, including construction, automobiles, electronics, and healthcare. Furthermore, the oil industry provides raw materials for the production of many goods, ranging from clothing to cosmetics.

However, despite the undeniable importance of the oil industry, it also faces challenges. Oil consumption leads to the depletion of reserves and negative environmental consequences such as water and air pollution and climate change. As a result, the global economy and the oil industry face the challenge of finding alternative energy sources and continuing to develop environmentally sustainable technologies (Shakatreh, Mansour, & Alatyat, 2022).

Overall, the oil industry plays a central role in the global economy by providing energy and raw materials for various industries, generating economic growth, and offering millions of jobs. However, given climate change and the depletion of reserves, the future of the oil industry requires finding more sustainable and greener solutions to ensure the long-term development of the global economy.

3. The Relationship Between Oil and Economic Development

Oil is one of the most important natural resources affecting economic development, playing a vital role in stimulating economic growth for both producing and consuming countries (Mustafa, Hammoodi, & Alsaady, 2024). The relationship between oil and economic development is evident in several key aspects, including (Mustafa, Hammoodi, & Alsaady, 2024):

- **Contribution of Oil to GDP:** The oil sector is a core component of the GDP in producing countries, serving as a major source of government revenue through exports and tax revenues. In many oil-rich nations, oil revenues significantly contribute to funding developmental projects such as infrastructure, education, and healthcare.
- **Stimulating Investments and Infrastructure:** The oil sector generates substantial financial returns, enabling governments to invest in developing infrastructure such as road networks, ports, electricity, and water systems. This enhances economic development and creates an attractive environment for both foreign and domestic investments (Shakatreh, Mansour, & Alatyat, 2022).
- **Job Creation and Supporting Related Sectors:** Although the oil industry itself is not highly labor-intensive, it stimulates the growth of other related sectors such as petrochemical industries,

transportation, logistics, and maintenance services. Additionally, spending oil revenues creates job opportunities in non-oil sectors such as tourism, trade, and manufacturing.

- **Impact on Trade Balance and Foreign Reserves:** Oil exports are a primary source of foreign currency, enhancing the trade balance stability of producing countries. Oil revenues help reduce trade deficits and increase foreign reserves, which in turn gives governments greater capacity to finance economic development projects (Mustafa, et al., 2019).
- **Fluctuations in Oil Prices and Their Economic Impact:** Oil price volatility presents a significant challenge to the sustainability of economic development in producing countries. A sharp decline in oil prices leads to reduced government revenues, affecting the implementation of development projects, while rising prices may lead to increased public spending and inflation.
- **Oil's Impact on Economic Diversification:** Many oil-producing countries are highly reliant on oil revenues, making them vulnerable to economic shocks when prices fall. To achieve sustainable economic development, these countries aim to diversify their economies by investing in other sectors such as renewable energy, industry, and services, thus reducing dependence on oil as the primary source of income.
- **Environmental Impact and Sustainable Development:** Despite the economic benefits of oil, it has negative environmental impacts such as pollution and carbon emissions, posing challenges for sustainable development. Consequently, many countries are developing strategies for clean energy and investing in environmental technologies to mitigate the negative effects of the oil industry (Mustafa, Moamin, & Dahlia, 2022).

Finally, the relationship between oil and economic development is closely tied to the country's ability to effectively manage its oil resources. While oil provides significant opportunities for economic growth, over-reliance on it may lead to economic volatility and financial instability. Therefore, achieving sustainable economic development requires income diversification, prudent management of oil revenues, and attention to environmental and social aspects to ensure long-term growth sustainability.

4. Proposed Model for Taxation of Oil Companies

The current tax system based on taxing financial results (gross profit, net income) will reduce the costs for extractive companies and the tax burden, as taxes will be levied on the profits of production companies. In this case, the estimated profit rate would be 50%, but it can be adjusted depending on the total accumulated return on investment. The introduction of tax on financial results can ensure the profitability of production in new, hard-to-access oil fields that lack infrastructure facilities.

Through our study and review of numerous Arab and foreign studies, it is evident that there are several challenges in developing the differentiation or tax disparity in oil and gas production. One of the most significant issues is the continuous changes in the procedures for calculating tax rates on mineral extraction, customs duties, and those imposed on oil exports, which complicates the process. Financial and estimative analyses have shown that if the prices of raw materials, oil, and gas in foreign markets are set for a long period below \$25 per barrel, it is possible that the budget will not receive the required tax and customs payments for oil and gas extraction, especially from undiscovered fields or those that are difficult to access. This is because oil production becomes unprofitable in such cases. Additionally, a gradual increase in oil and gas production in new fields could lead to mandatory preventive measures to increase the tax burden on producing companies in order to renew and finance budget revenues.

In the current Russian tax system, even with the use of indicators that consider technological, financial, and economic production factors, which should fully account for the production conditions of different raw materials, oil, and gas, particularly those that are difficult to access,

profitable production cannot be guaranteed. This ideal variable can only be achieved in relation to individual factors when applying correction factors. Moreover, transactions used within the framework of the modern tax system can be partially employed when calculating taxes on mineral extraction in some deposits where preferential taxes are applied, and for all other types of deposits. It is necessary to consider factors such as the depth of the well and the field size. Based on the results of tax analysis for raw material, oil, and gas production, it is concluded that in conditions of low production levels in existing fields and those unfit for operation with low profitability, the additional use of the current tax system becomes unacceptable. This applies even to the advantages provided by the tax system, where production in these fields is taxed using a special rate mechanism (percentage), and a mechanism is established that takes into account the specificities of oil and gas extraction. The approach used in creating different preferential tax systems leads to the fact that this set of measures applied to taxation on oil and gas production today is unacceptable for extracting various raw materials from new fields, especially those that are difficult to access, such as budget revenues (Ibrahim, 2018).

Due to the benefits gained by some companies through the differential mechanism, taxes are compensated by increasing the tax burden on other companies. Taxation for oil and gas production should be developed considering all the conditions that affect the size of the taxable base formed during raw material extraction. Since solving the tax issue depends on the complexity of determining the tax subject for oil and gas extraction in hard-to-access fields, the algorithm for calculating tax rates for oil and gas production in such fields, which could be adopted by modern tax systems, should take into account the profitability and price volatility of oil and gas. This can be represented by the following formula:

$$SN = NB \cdot BS \cdot Kp \cdot Kec \cdot P \quad (1)$$

Where:

SN - The amount of tax on the extraction of raw materials, oil, and gas from hard-to-reach deposits.

NB - The tax base for fuel production in hard-to-reach fields.

BS - The basic standard upon which the tax rate for the extraction of raw materials, oil, and gas is determined.

p - Adjustment for oil price volatility.

Kes - Correction for production conditions.

P - Profitability adjustment.

These transactions, used to calculate the rate, have a universal property, and their use in the current tax system will fully account for the production conditions of different types of raw materials.

The proposed approach, which is a set of calculations for profitability factors and raw material price fluctuations, enables the identification of a new direction in the development of taxes on oil and gas production. It also works on formulating the basic requirements for calculating the tax rate on raw material, oil, and gas production in hard-to-reach fields, considering the profitability and fluctuations in raw material prices to predict tax revenue level standards.

Here, the researchers propose the establishment of specific factors for the development of the tax system, through which the priorities of financial policy should be considered. This is not only in the model for solving the issue of maximizing the current budget revenue from companies involved in oil and gas extraction but also in creating a unified model mechanism to ensure the sustainable

development of the oil and gas sector as a whole and stimulate investment activities in exploration and the development of new mineral deposits. This approach illustrates a comprehensive and integrated direction for fiscal policy regarding the taxation of mining companies (Kryzanowski, Perrakis, & Zhong, 2020).

As a result, it can be concluded that the current fiscal policy should aim to create such appropriate tax incentives for extractive companies. We can say that the most important conditions to consider when adjusting fiscal policy in the field of oil and gas production are:

- Differentiation between elements of fiscal policy aimed at considering regional, production, and geographical characteristics of production when determining tax standards for specific companies.
- Compensation for the financial burden on mining companies through the creation of alternative tax systems (such as income tax, tax on financial results, etc.).

It should be noted that these methods are often applied randomly. The choice of this method or that, or their combination, always and approximately depends on the current political situation in the country and the state of the budget. Therefore, oil and gas companies cannot reliably predict the selection of prices, tools, and conditions for applying the appropriate methods. As a result, negative aspects constantly emerge, reducing the attractiveness of investment in the industry and diminishing key economic indicators of activity (Mark, 2021).

In this study, a specific factor is proposed to determine the maximum cost amount that reduces the tax base for taxes collected on the profits from the extraction of raw materials, oil, and gas in new and particularly hard-to-reach fields. It is recommended to use this ratio from the moment the oil and gas company begins to generate profit until it reaches a certain level of depletion (for example, 5%).

$$A = Q_n \cdot P_n - C_n Q_{n-1} \cdot P_n - C_{n-1} \cdot E_n \cdot E_{n-1} \quad (2)$$

Where:

A specific factor.

P_n is the actual selling price of the raw materials, oil, and gas produced during the analyzed period.

Q_n is the sales volume of the raw materials, oil, and gas produced during the analyzed period.

Q_{n-1} is the sales volume of the raw materials, oil, and gas produced during the previous period.

C_n is the production cost of the raw materials, oil, and gas in the analyzed period.

C_{n-1} is the production cost of the raw materials, oil, and gas in the previous period.

E_n is the recovery factor for the analyzed period, tons / thousand cubic meters.

E_{n-1} is the recovery factor for the previous period, tons / thousand cubic meters.

As a result of the findings from this study and research, scientific and practical recommendations have been formulated regarding the use of the differentiation (variation) model in taxation on oil and gas production, specifically in terms of imposing taxes on the export activities of mining and extraction companies. These recommendations are based on determining the cost of raw material exports, taking into account the actual volume of raw materials exported and the fluctuations in oil prices in global markets.

Through the analysis of the financial implications of introducing the proposed tax on raw material exports within the tax system, a model for taxation has been developed within the framework of the modern tax system. Additionally, the proposed tax option for raw material, oil, and gas exports has been outlined.

Fifth - The Proposed Tax Model

It becomes clear to us at this time and in the subsequent periods, when the tax on the export of raw materials, oil, and gas will be in effect under the production conditions in new and hard-to-reach fields, that if oil and gas production increases in these fields, substantial financial revenues will be generated. These revenues will, in turn, fund the federal budget. Here, we must focus on the necessity of diversifying funding sources for the budget through multiple sources.

The initial values of the parameters for the raw material export tax model and its calculation, considering the fluctuations of their prices in the global market and the conversion of payment transactions based on the chosen financial option, are presented in Financial Policy Option Table 1.

Table 1. Tax Model for Exporting Fuels Considering Price Fluctuations in the Global Market

Unit of Measurement for the Model	Details
Export Period	2015/2024
Price per Barrel of Oil	For the specified period, in US Dollars
The price of exported oil per ton for the tax period is determined by the following formula:	$S = (P + P1 + + Pn) : n$ <p>S is the market price of the crude oil and gas condensates sold during the tax period. Pn is the daily average market price of the crude oil sold during the tax period. n is the number of days within the tax period.</p>
Export Duty on Oil per Ton	US Dollars
Price of Exported Oil per Ton	Iraqi Dinar (excluding fees)
Domestic Oil Price per Ton	Iraqi Dinar
Export Duty Rate	0-50%
Export Tax Rate on Raw Materials	50%
Conversion Factors from Barrels to Tons	$KB.av. = (V1 \times KB.1 + V2 \times KB.2 + Vn \times KB.n) / \text{Total Execution}$, where V1, V2, ... Vn - the volumes of each batch of crude oil and crude oil products sold for export during the tax period. KB.1, KB.2 ... + KB.n - conversion factors from barrels to metric tons, as indicated in the quality passport for each corresponding batch, based on data from the measuring device at the delivery and receiving point of the crude oil and crude oil products transportation organization at the start of the export route. n is the number of shipments of crude oil and crude oil products sold for export during the tax period. V Total Sales - the total sales of crude oil and crude oil products during the tax period.

Source: Prepared by the researchers.

Through the presentation of Table 1, which clearly displays the proposed tax model for the export of oil, gas, and raw materials, it follows that the initial data provided for calculating the comparison of payment volumes under the current and proposed tax systems indicates that, based on the final results of applying the proposed tax system, taxing the export of raw materials, oil, and gas would

generate a larger total amount of public financial payments. However, this would be less dependent on the efficiency of the activities of mining, oil, and gas companies.

Sixth – Conclusion

Based on this, the following conclusions and recommendations can be formulated.

Conclusions

1. The study revealed that strategic management adjusts and activates fiscal policy movement in a way that guarantees the strategic future and enables adaptation to the surrounding environment and conditions.
2. The specificity of implementing the tax system for the state's fiscal policy in the current stage of economic relations development is determined by the current tax tool system. The key tools of fiscal policy are noted to be the principles of formation, the mechanism for calculating the base, the pricing size, and the procedures for making financial payments. These tools enabled the state's fiscal policy mechanisms to define the distinctive features of implementing the fiscal policy in times of modern economic transitions.
3. Trade in oil and gas has become part of economic practice, particularly in the context of widespread speculative transactions. The increase in oil price volatility over the past twenty-five years, on one hand, accompanies inflationary processes and intensified growth, but on the other hand, contributes to a significant rise in investments designed to support oil and gas production.
4. The lack of organized priorities in the implementation of the tax policy by the state leads to unsatisfactory results in the economic domain. Among the tools used by the state to stimulate and develop natural resource management, taxes hold an important position. Specifically, the economic goals involve increasing the development level of the real sector, stimulating the economic activity of entities in environmental management, and mitigating the acute issues emerging in oil and gas production and sales.
5. The current tax system for the extractive industry of raw materials, oil, and gas is ineffective in terms of distributing the tax burden across new fields. These subjects face burdensome tax obligations at the start of their production, as this occurs without considering the profitability level at the production's initiation. At the same time, as a result of the changes introduced in the form of new taxes on additional income from oil production, there are prerequisites for creating an effective tax system that maximizes not only consideration for the development conditions of mineral deposits and raw materials but also takes into account the volatility of oil prices.
6. The lack of clarity in the results of strategic management programs leads to higher tax evasion rates and reduced public compliance with tax payments.

Recommendations

1. Strategic management should make changes and adjustments to its plans and strategies, seeking more realistic strategies that can address the needs required by tax administration, while enhancing the ability for strategic thinking and establishing a clear long-term vision capable of predicting future events and maximizing revenue.
2. To ensure effective taxation, it is essential to consider the impact on the tax base size under different circumstances. The tax base size depends on oil and gas sales revenues and the profitability of companies engaged in their extraction. Therefore, it is crucial to account for the profitability level achieved by using a reduction factor that reflects the minimum profitability

threshold. In modern tax systems, this is not regulated by legislative rules concerning the mechanism to ensure a minimum profitability level for companies engaged in oil and gas extraction.

3. Efforts should be made to increase the integration of strategic management culture so that it becomes part of the workforce's culture.

4. Introducing a primary tax audit institution. Such an institution would, on one hand, help taxpayers significantly reduce tax risks while providing assurances in their dealings with tax authorities. On the other hand, it would allow tax authorities to conduct preliminary tax audits on taxpayers' activities, reduce time costs during subsequent tax audits, and assist in combating tax evasion.

5. Efforts should be made to improve the transfer pricing tax rules. Over the three years these transfer pricing rules have been in effect, the practice of applying them indicates the need to enhance tax oversight on the use of transfer pricing.

6. Adopting a policy of rapid economic reforms, including the creation of a form of tax revenue to expand the tax base, through the implementation of economic, commercial, and financial policies that contribute to revenue diversification.

References

Aktionova, A. A. (2017). The flexibility of fiscal policy in the context of cyclical development of the economy. *Finance and Credit*, (3).

Alive, B. Kh. (2017). Strategic guidelines for improving the tax system of Russia. *Finance and Credit*, (42), 42–47.

Dahlia, A. A., Mustafa, A. I., & Yasir, J. S. (2023). The role of information management systems in the implementation of the digital economy development strategy. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(5), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i5.1419>

Dahlia, A. A., Mustafa, A. I., & Yasir, J. S. (2023). The role of knowledge management in developing the state's financial policy in light of economic fluctuations. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 6(10), 89–100.

Falko, A. I., & Somina, I. V. (2022). International practices of assessing digitalization as a determinant of the innovative development of the economy: Research based on the index method. *Issues of the Innovative Economy*, 12(1), 595–606. <https://doi.org/10.18334/vincc.12.1.113872>

Guidolin, M., Hansen, E., & Pedio, M. (2019). Cross-asset contagion in the financial crisis: A Bayesian time-varying parameter approach. *Journal of Financial Markets*, 45, 83–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.finmar.2019.04.001>

Ibrahim, M. A. (2018). Key problems of the fiscal policy of the state in the conditions of the decline in the level of the economy of the Russian Federation. *Bulletin of the University (State University of Management)*.

Karaev, R. A., Mikailova, R. N., Safarli, I. I., Sadykhova, N. Y., & Imamverdieva, H. F. (2018). Cognitive tools for dynamic analysis of business strategies of enterprises. *Business Informatics*, (1)(43), 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.17323/1998-0663.2018.1.7.16>

Kryzanowski, L., Perrakis, S., & Zhong, R. (2020). Financial oligopolies and parallel exclusion in the credit default swap markets. *Journal of Financial Markets*, 47, 100606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.finmar.2020.100606>

- Mark, H. M. (2021). Creating public value: The core idea of strategic management in government. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 6(1), 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2021.v6i1.219>
- Moamin, M. S., Yasir, J. S., Dahlia, A. A., & Mustafa, A. I. (2024). Strategic leadership of information systems in the development of the digital economy. *Indonesian Journal of Law and Economics Review*, 19(4). <https://doi.org/10.21070/ijler.v19i4.1275>
- Muresianu, A., & Watson, G. (2021). Reviewing the federal tax treatment of research & development expenses. *Fiscal Fact*, (759).
- Mustafa, A. I., Brattsev, V. I., & AlSaady, W., Hammoodi, L. K. (2019). Russia's fiscal policy in the context of oil price volatility. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical & Control Systems*, 11(09-Special Issue), 1210–1213.
- Mustafa, A. I., Hammoodi, L. K., & Alsaady, W. (2024). Artificial intelligence as a tool for financial policy efficiency in the context of digitalization. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 9(3), 1–17.
- Mustafa, A. I., Moamin, M. S., & Dahlia, A. A. (2022). The role of financial policy and strategic planning in the development of the state economy. *Social Science Journal, Res Militaris*, 12(2), 4827.
- Pilipenko, O. I. (2012). Anti-crisis fiscal policy of the state in the context of positive economic theory. *Vestnik RUDN. Series: Economy*, (3), 25–29.
- Romanov, A. N., & Kolchen, C. P. (2017). Taxes and taxation. Moscow.
- Shakatreh, M., Mansour, A. M. A., & Alatyat, Z. A. (2022). Corporate tax features in Jordan affecting business decisions: Strengthening finance accountability in emerging economies. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 7(4), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2022.v7i4.e739>
- Shchegoleva, N. G., & Malsagov, T. G. (2019). Digital technologies in the economy and ecology of "smart cities". *Problems of Theory and Practice of Management*, (3–4), 12–22.
- Tretyakova, M., Kuznetsova, T., & Polyakova, T. (Eds.). (2024). *Sustainable economic development: Complex interrelations*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54383-8>
- Vallega, A. (2003). *Sustainable ocean governance: A geographical perspective*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203209721>
- Wang, X. (2019). Financial sector policies and current account imbalances: Cross-country evidence. *Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy*, 25(4), 757–782. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13547860.2019.1710426>

